

Artigo:

Challenges and environmental performance of the jeans production chain

Desafios e desempenho ambiental da cadeia de produção de jeans

Desafíos y desempeño ambiental de la cadena de producción de jeans

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Resumo

O estudo analisou os efeitos da política de descentralização econômica e produtiva do Brasil, examinando os impactos ambientais de empresas de vestuário localizadas em um polo regional do Nordeste. A análise considerou a infraestrutura da cadeia de suprimentos e de produção, bem como os impactos ambientais da fabricação de jeans, desde o cultivo do algodão até a distribuição final. A pesquisa utilizou a Avaliação do Ciclo de Vida (ACV) baseada nas normas NBR ISO 14040 e 14044 (2009) para identificar os impactos do ciclo de vida de duas fábricas de jeans no Piauí. Dados primários e secundários, além do Ecoinvent, foram utilizados com o software OpenLCA. Os principais resultados incluem impactos significativos da escassez hídrica no processamento do jeans, enquanto a produção de algodão no Cerrado brasileiro apresentou menor consumo de água devido à topografia e ao clima favoráveis. No entanto, os insumos agrícolas contribuíram para a eutrofização e a acidificação do solo. O alto consumo de energia e o transporte na tecelagem e na fabricação resultaram em emissões de CO₂ e oxidantes. A atual cadeia de suprimentos da indústria de vestuário do país tende a desfavorecer regiões remotas em termos de impactos ambientais. Os resultados deste estudo demonstram que o fortalecimento da autonomia regional poderia fomentar cadeias de suprimentos têxteis mais sustentáveis. Considerando as condições e características específicas da indústria têxtil brasileira, este estudo forneceu informações valiosas sobre as operações e o contexto de empresas situadas em polos regionais.

Palavras-Chave: Setor de Fabricação Têxtil e de Vestuário. Cadeia de suprimentos têxtil. Desenvolvimento regional.

Abstract

The study analyzed the effects of Brazil's economic and productive decentralization policy by examining the environmental impacts of clothing companies located in a regional hub in the Northeast. It analyzed production and supply chain infrastructure and the environmental impacts of jeans manufacturing, from cotton cultivation to final distribution. The research used LCA based on NBR ISO 14040 and 14044 (2009) to identify life cycle impacts from two jeans manufacturers in Piauí. Primary and secondary data and Ecoinvent were used with OpenLCA software. Key findings include significant water scarcity impacts from jeans processing, while cotton production in the Brazilian Cerrado showed lower water use due to favorable topography and climate. However, agricultural inputs contributed to eutrophication and soil acidification. High energy use and transport in weaving and manufacturing led to CO₂ and oxidant emissions. The current supply chain of the country's apparel industry tends to disadvantage remote regions in terms of environmental impacts. The results of this study show that strengthening regional autonomy could foster more sustainable textile supply chains. Considering the specific conditions and characteristics of the Brazilian textile industry, this study has provided valuable insights into the operations and context of companies situated in regional hubs.

Key-words: Textile and Clothing Manufacturing Sector. Textile supply chain. Regional development.

Resumen

El estudio analizó los efectos de la política de descentralización económica y productiva de Brasil mediante el examen de los impactos ambientales de las empresas textiles ubicadas en un centro regional del noreste. Se analizó la infraestructura de producción y cadena de suministro, así como los impactos ambientales de la fabricación de jeans, desde el cultivo del algodón hasta la distribución final. La investigación utilizó un análisis de ciclo de vida (ACV) basado en las normas NBR ISO 14040 y 14044 (2009) para identificar los impactos en el ciclo de vida de dos fabricantes de jeans en Piauí. Se utilizaron datos primarios y secundarios, así como Ecoinvent, con el software OpenLCA. Los hallazgos clave incluyen impactos significativos en la escasez de agua durante el procesamiento de jeans, mientras que la producción de algodón en el Cerrado brasileño mostró un menor uso de agua debido a la topografía y el clima favorables. Sin embargo, los insumos agrícolas contribuyeron a la eutrofización y la acidificación del suelo. El alto consumo de energía y el transporte en el tejido y la fabricación generaron emisiones de CO₂ y oxidantes. La actual cadena de suministro de la industria textil del país tiende a perjudicar a las regiones remotas en términos de impactos ambientales. Los resultados de este estudio muestran que el fortalecimiento de la autonomía regional podría promover cadenas de suministro textiles más sostenibles. Considerando las condiciones y características específicas de la industria textil brasileña, este estudio ha proporcionado información valiosa sobre las operaciones y el contexto de las empresas ubicadas en centros regionales.

Palabras-Clave: Sector textil y de confección. Cadena de suministro textil. Desarrollo regional.

INTRODUCTION

Environmental sustainability has been a prominent topic, especially in the textile and apparel industries due to environmental impacts. These sectors drive a vast production and complex chain, resource-intensive, creating jobs and fostering the development of countries (Ellen MacArthur Foundation, 2017; Luo et al., 2021; Zhao & Lin, 2019).

The life cycle of textile products reveals significant environmental impacts. Among them, intense water and energy consumption, greenhouse gas emissions, chemical and solid waste generation (Hackett; Tara, 2015; Piontek; Müller, 2018; Watson; Wiedemann, 2019), water and soil pollution, both resulting from chemical waste discharges from dyeing and laundry processes, microfibers, clothing maintenance (Cinperi et al., 2019; Henry et al., 2019; Madhav et al., 2018; United Nations Economic Commission for Europe (UNECE), 2018). The use of fertilizers, pesticides, insecticides, and agricultural chemicals for fiber cultivation poses direct and indirect threats to human health and aquatic and terrestrial life (Amutha 2017; Hussain; Wahab 2018; Witkoski; Morgenstern, 2021).

The fashion industry produces twenty percent of global wastewater and ten percent of global carbon emissions. In addition, it causes plastic pollution in the oceans due to the washing of plastic-based fabrics such as polyester, nylon or acrylic (UNECE, 2018). In cotton cultivation, which is one of the main raw materials for clothing, mechanized activities with high energy consumption are commonly used. This energy is utilized in the form of electricity or fossil fuels for operating irrigation pumps, tractors, harvesters, and various other machinery (Amutha, 2017; La Rosa; Grammatikos, 2019).

The clothing use phase, that includes the consumer's washing, has been pointed out as one of the largest contributors to the product's life cycle impact (Baydar et al., 2015; Manda et al., 2015; Zhang et al., 2015). It demands actions

for public awareness about the consumption consequences on the environment and greater involvement of industry, governments and sectors to influence consumers to buy less clothes or adopt reuse or recycling (Manda et al., 2015; Peters et al., 2021; Vesterinen & Syrjälä, 2022).

Studies indicate that the sustainable fashion industry may represent a new market segment with alternative innovations aimed at reducing environmental impact (Blatt et al., 2020; İvedi et al., 2022; Pal & Gander, 2018; Zamani et al., 2017). The fast fashion industry contributes significantly to pollution due to its varied styles and washing methods. Peters et al. (2021) found that clothing and footwear consumption has increasingly impacted global climate change over the past 15 years. China, India, the United States, and Brazil, as the top textile producers, significantly contribute to this issue.

Brazil's textile and clothing industry is socio-economically important, with numerous production hubs nationwide. The Associação Brasileira da Indústria Têxtil e de Confecção (ABIT) (2022) states that Brazil is a major clothing and textile producer, covering the entire production chain. It ranks as the fourth largest global producer of knitwear and clothing, and fifth in textile and denim production and consumption. The production volume has reached 2.16 million tons per year, resulting in the creation of 1.34 million direct and indirect jobs (Instituto de Estudos e Marketing Industrial (IEMI), 2022).

National production primarily targets the domestic market. This necessitates importing textiles from Asian countries like China, India, Pakistan, South Korea, Taiwan, Indonesia, Malaysia, Thailand, and Bangladesh, which increased their production from the 1980s (Confederação Nacional da Indústria, 2017; IEMI, 2022; Mendes Júnior, 2017). The country has recently shown gradual progress in the sector during the post-COVID-19 period, with clear signs of productive recovery and growing exports (Mendes Júnior, 2021).

Furthermore, Brazil is an important producer and exporter of cotton (Annual Report 2020, 2020; Associação Brasileira dos Produtores de Algodão

(ABRAPA), 2022). Cotton production is concentrated in the Northeast region, specifically within the states of Maranhão (MA), Piauí (PI), and Bahia (BA). However, the Center-West region accounts for the largest production volume (Bezerra et al., 2015; Instituto Brasileiro de Geografia e Estatística (IBGE), 2020). Cotton cultivation in the Center-West region is predominant in Mato Grosso (MT) and Mato Grosso do Sul (MS) (Associação Mato-Grossense dos Produtores de Algodão, 2014).

The spinning and weaving stages are primarily conducted in the Southeast, while the sewing processes take place mainly in the Northeast and South regions (Costa; Rocha, 2009; Departamento de Pesquisas e Estudos Econômicos (DEPEC), 2017). According to Mendes Júnior (2021), the gross production value of the Brazilian textile and clothing sector is representative in the South and Southeast regions, almost 80% of joint participation, while the Northeast, secondly, contributes 17%.

The State of Paraná (PR) and the Northeast Semi-arid region stand out in the sewing of clothes in general, including jeans (DEPEC, 2017; Lima; Cavalcanti Júnior, 2019). In Brazil, there are just over 20,000 industrial clothing production units, with 71.6% being micro-industries, 25.7% small industries and 2.7% medium and large industries, representing the national clothing manufacturing sector together (IEMI, 2022; Prado and Suzuki, 2021). Figure 1 shows the distribution of the largest concentrations by stage of the textile chain in Brazil.

Figure 1 - Distribution of the largest concentrations of cotton cultivation, textile production (with spinning, weaving, and clothing) in Brazil

Source: Authors.

The Northeast excels in producing jeans and casual fashion (Barreto et al., 2018; Caldas & Lima, 2009; Fernandes & Silva Filho, 2017; Lima & Cavalcanti Júnior, 2019; Oliveira da Silva & Dos Santos, 2021; Silva Filho et al., 2021). The northeastern clothing market plays a significant role in the region's and country's economy, enhancing employment and income, and contributing to local development, including technological advancements in industries (Oliveira da Silva & Dos Santos, 2021). Piauí has demonstrated significant progress in the textile industry, accounting for a national share of 17.4%. Additionally, it has achieved a 7.6% share in the clothing and accessories manufacturing sector, thereby contributing to local employment (Bezerra et al., 2015).

To boost the economy, Brazil's government implemented policies from the 1930s to the 1970s to promote development in marginalized regions. This aimed to reduce the concentration of industrial investment in the South and Southeast, which widened the economic gap between the core and peripheral

areas (Santos; Silva Filho, 2021). To address this situation, federal agencies were created to assess the development potential of various Brazilian regions. In the 1950s, two major initiatives in the Northeast were the creation of Superintendency for the Development of the Northeast (SUDENE) and Working Group for the Development of the Northeast (GTDN). The national plans aimed to promote integration and boost investment in energy, transportation, basic industries, food, and education to encourage balanced and inclusive growth (Santos & Silva Filho, 2021).

Although these initiatives focused on regional development—both economic and structural— their impact also encompassed environmental aspects. The creation of new productive hubs within the country reshaped territorial, social, and ecological dynamics. However, it is evident that the policies adopted were primarily driven by political and economic interests, with limited attention on sustainability (Da Silva et al., 2019).

Thus, this study aims to analyze the effects of productive decentralization policies on a textile and clothing hub in Northeast Brazil, which has come to play a significant role in the national economy. The focus is on its environmental implications within the broader process of the country's geographic reorganization of production.

Considering the specific conditions and characteristics of the Brazilian textile industry, this study has provided valuable insights into the operations and context of companies situated in regional hubs. The research examines how the dynamics and infrastructure of this industry contribute to the environmental impacts generated by the sector. Consequently, this article presents the environmental performance of jeans production, encompassing all stages of the production process — from cotton cultivation to distribution to the end consumer — while considering the current infrastructure conditions of the textile chain in Brazil.

To evaluate the environmental performance of two jeans produced in a manufacturing hub located in northeastern Brazil, specifically in Piauí state,

the Life Cycle Assessment (LCA) methodology was employed. LCA is widely used due to its applicability in indicating critical points, in terms of environmental impacts, and allowing recommendations for decision-making even in the definition of the raw materials (Sharpe et al., 2022). In addition, it allows analyzing how geographical, climatic, frequency of use (linked to consumption habits), useful life, energy consumption in the production system, among others, influence environmental impacts in several categories (F. Chen et al., 2021).

This article expands the knowledge about the environmental impacts of the textile and apparel sector in Brazil, particularly focusing on the Northeast region, which has significant potential for regional development and economic opportunities. Additionally, it encourages further studies on environmental issues in this area, emphasizing the application of Life Cycle Assessment (LCA) in the textile sector.

2 MATERIAL AND METHODS

2.1 Goal and scope definition

The Life Cycle Assessment (LCA) was performed following the guidelines of NBR ISO 14040 (2009) and NBR ISO 14044 (2009), encompassing four stages: goal and scope definition, Life Cycle Inventory (LCI), Life Cycle Impact Assessment (LCIA), and results interpretation. The LCA aimed to analyze the environmental performance of two models of jeans produced in a hub located in Campo Maior, PI. This city is known for its jeans produced and it's a reference to Piauí state.

The functional unit was a pair of adult jeans made of cotton with indigo blue dyeing. Each jeans model was provided by different companies. To maintain anonymity, the companies were designated as company A and company B, with their respective products named A and B. Company A provided data on a blue men's jeans made of 100% cotton, with an average size

of 1.17m (height), weight 0.277g (grammage of 9 Oz/yd²), with washing and softening treatment (superstone). Company B provided data on a blue women's jeans made of 100% cotton, with an average size of 1.25m and weight of 0.430g (grammage 9 Oz/yd²), with bleaching and whitening treatment (destroyed). The reference flow was the average mass of each pair of jeans, and the function of the analyzed system was clothing.

The selected industries adequately represent the industrial scenario of the hub, making it unnecessary to incorporate other manufacturing units to obtain data, since their activities reflect the context of the study in a representative way. The companies were intentionally selected because they are the two largest in the production hub, which serve as a reference for other smaller industries. No allocation was needed in the clothing industry since only jeans were being produced.

The study covers processes from the beginning of production to distribution, including cotton production, processing, spinning, weaving denim fabric, sewing jeans, laundry processing, and wholesale and retail distribution. Figure 2 illustrates the included and excluded phases in the system boundary.

Figure 2 - Life cycle of jeans and delimitation of the system boundary, including transportation

Source: Authors.

The LCA model included transportation between production phases. Transport from the cotton processor to the spinning company was part of the cotton cultivation model as both are in Mato Grosso do Sul, avoiding value duplication (Morita, 2013). The journey from the sewing factory in Campo Maior to the retail store in Teresina, Piauí's capital, was considered using Google Maps distances. Similarly, the transportation of the jeans to and from the laundry, located in Teresina, and the sewing factory was calculated.

The modeling utilized primary data obtained through direct measurements from two clothing industries and the jeans processing laundry that serves both companies. Additionally, secondary data sourced from the Ecoinvent Database and relevant literature were employed to model the phases of cotton cultivation, processing, and the textile sector (spinning and weaving). The OpenLCA software was employed for data analysis, prioritizing the use of Brazilian data when selecting Ecoinvent processes. In cases where Brazilian

data were unavailable, global coverage data (GLO) or "rest of world" (RoW) data were utilized.

Regarding geographical coverage, cotton cultivation data is derived from production activities conducted in the Center-West region of Brazil, specifically Mato Grosso do Sul. Data related to the textile sector, including spinning and processing, is sourced from the Southeast region, particularly São Paulo. In terms of technological coverage, both primary and secondary sources reflect the current technologies employed in jeans manufacturing within the geographical scope of this study.

For the Life Cycle Inventory (LCI), the product system processes were defined, outlining inputs such as raw materials, energy, water, and chemicals, as well as outputs including emissions, discharges, solid waste, and finished products as illustrated in Figure 3. Supplementary Material 1 provides detailed information on the input and output flows that make up the life cycle inventory.

Figure 3 - Input and output flows of the product system by production stage of jeans

Source: Authors.

In the model process, a distinction was made between the jeans processing stages of laundry and sewing due to their occurrence in different production environments and companies. This allowed for a detailed analysis of each stage's environmental impacts. Due to a lack of records and company restrictions, data on firewood thermal energy and laundry emissions came from secondary sources.

Air emissions from the weaving, spinning, and jeans processing processes were not included in the study, as specified in the Associação Brasileira de Normas Técnicas (ABNT), (2009a, 2009b) guidelines. No public records on air quality monitoring in the sector studied were found. National air quality criteria were recently updated through Resolution No. 506, dated July 5, 2024, which mandates national standards for air quality monitoring.

The impacts of the textile and clothing industry, from fiber production to consumer use, include the utilization of natural resources such as water and land, the emission of greenhouse gases, and pollution of air, soil, and water. Additionally, it involves toxicity, soil degradation, and a reduction in biodiversity (S. Chen et al., 2023; Moazzem et al., 2021; Periyasamy & Periyasami, 2023). To highlight the main impacts of textile processes, the LCIA considered the categories of Global Warming Potential (GWP), Terrestrial Acidification (TA), Potential Eutrophication (PE), Photochemical Ozone Formation (POF), and Water Scarcity. These categories are crucial and frequently addressed in LCA studies within the textile and clothing sector (Arduin, 2013; S. Chen et al., 2023).

Preference was given to methods reflecting the Brazilian context. (Mendes & Ometto, 2019) recommended evaluating Terrestrial Acidification using Recipe 2016 Midpoint (H), while (Castro et al., 2019) suggested AWARE for water scarcity. Other categories followed guidelines from the (Product Category Rules, 2021) for jeans, including Global Warming Potential by IPCC GWP 100a, Eutrophication Potential by CML-IA 2001 baseline, and Photochemical Oxidation Formation by ReCiPe Midpoint (H). These methods were chosen for their relevance to the product and comprehensive analysis scope.

Uncertainty and sensitivity analyses were performed as part of the LCA study interpretation. Using OpenLCA software's Pedigree Matrix, data scores (1 to 5) input for reliability, completeness, and temporal, geographical, and technological correlation were assigned. Monte Carlo Simulation with a Logarithmic distribution, 1,000 interactions, and a 95% confidence interval was used to calculate the mean and standard deviation (ABNT, 2009b).

Data on sewing and laundry, collected in 2022, was deemed highly reliable and scored a 1. This data reflects the current operations in the jeans life cycle accurately. Data on cotton cultivation, processing, spinning, and weaving were rated reliable and suitable for the study, scoring a 2 in the Pedigree

Matrix. The primary data references from Morita (2013) and Morita et al. (2020) were updated between 2013 and 2018. The geographical coverage of all phases accurately represents the study regions. These regions have the highest production volumes in their respective segments within Brazil, making them relevant for applying this data in Life Cycle Assessment (LCA). Regarding technological coverage, the data was compatible with the context of the investigation, as it was obtained from Brazilian companies involved in the textile and clothing manufacturing sector.

Both primary and secondary data demonstrate high completeness, covering all aspects of the jeans sewing process in the LCA study. Detailed measurements from sewing factories included energy, water, material consumption, and solid waste generation. The specifics of jeans production, such as machinery and resource types, were considered. Secondary data accurately reflected Brazilian conditions, incorporating agricultural dynamics and national textile studies.

The data sources were highly reliable, scoring 2 due to consistent verification and validation. Primary data was collected through direct field measurements following LCA standards. Secondary data came from peer-reviewed articles and reputable scientific publications in environmental and LCA fields, ensuring methodological robustness and result validity.

In turn, sensitivity analysis involved new scenarios, in addition to the standard scenario, from the most critical processes hotspots for the categories used in this study. With the new values of the indicators of the environmental impact categories, the percentage reduction for each category was calculated to analyze whether the changes in the results were significant (greater than or equal to 10%) (Associação Brasileira de Normas Técnicas, 2009a). This allowed for reflections on the Brazilian textile production chain.

3 RESULTS

3.1 Description of production process and companies

The sewing factories involved in the research have been in business for over 20 years, producing casual fashion and jeanswear for markets in Northeast Brazil, the North region, and the Federal District. These small companies focus on adult apparel, mainly targeting women. Each employ around 65 workers and produces about 10,000 jeans per month.

These companies, operating in the same market, utilize similar production strategies, technologies, and sales and distribution channels, including their own transportation. The raw materials for the jeans manufacturing production system in Campo Maior are sourced from suppliers located in various regions of Brazil, such as Santa Catarina, São Paulo, Paraná, Ceará, Sergipe, and Rio Grande do Norte. Road transport is the main method used to deliver these materials to sewing factories. Figure 4 shows the locations and routes of suppliers to the factories in Campo Maior.

Figure 4 - Locations and routes of raw material suppliers to the jeans production plant

Company A

Company B

Source: Authors.

Both sewing factories follow these stages for jeans production: creation, modeling, manual cutting with support, sewing and assembly, laundry treatment, finishing, and distribution. The companies lack an internal laundry system, reflecting local conditions as there is no laundry facility in Campo Maior. In this context, the jeans processing stage takes place in Teresina, situated 84 km from Campo Maior. This necessitates the transportation of the pieces both ways, managed by the laundry. The transportation is conducted via road using a vehicle owned by the laundry. Figure 5 visually depicts the jeans manufacturing production process of the two companies examined.

Figure 5 - Jeans manufacturing process flowchart

Source: Authors.

3.2 Life Cycle Impact Assessment

The environmental performance of jeans from companies A and B is detailed through indicators of the chosen impact categories. The results for the reference flow of the jeans studied are provided in Table 1. Figure 6 shows the environmental performance results in distributed percentage form.

Table 1 - Environmental performance results of the production of jeans

Impact category	Unity	Company A	Company B
Water Scarcity	m ³	29.80	106.15
Eutrophication Potential	kg PO ₄ ³⁻ eq	9.90E-03	1.51E-02
Terrestrial Acidification	kg SO ₂ eq	2.01E-02	2.93E-02
Photochemical Oxidation Formation	kg NMVOC eq	1.71E-02	2.31E-02
Global Warming Potential	kg CO ₂ eq	5.69	8.32

Source: Authors.

Figure 6 - Environmental performance percentual of the production of jeans

Source: Authors.

The water scarcity category, evaluated using the AWARE method, identified the laundry stage (jeans processing) as the primary contributor to water consumption within the jeans life cycle. Although the weaving phase had the second highest water consumption, its impact was minimal in comparison to the processing stage. For product A, total consumption was 29.80 m³, with laundry processing at 85% and weaving at 7.01%. For product B, total consumption was 106.15 m³, with jeans processing at 95.16% and weaving at 2.15%.

Jeans processing in laundry and weaving consumes a lot of water during desizing, washing, bleaching, and mercerizing to prepare the yarn, control temperature, improve texture, and remove residues or impurities (Hasanbeigi

& Price, 2015). As expected, Company B's jeans manufacturing consumes a lot of water due to multiple washes needed for the desired blue shade. Water scarcity in cotton cultivation contributed 1.36 m³ (4.59%) and 2.12 m³ (2%) to the life cycle of jeans from companies A and B, respectively.

The production, processing of cotton, jeans manufacturing, and sewing were notable in the PE results. Company A's jeans had an impact of 9.90E-03 kg PO₄³⁻eq, while Company B's was 1.51E-02 kg PO₄³⁻eq. The most significant impact came from the jeans washing process, with Company B's at 47.09% compared to Company A's 29.98%. The environmental impact of this phase was due to tap water use (product A: 7.55%, product B: 19.95%), energy consumption (product A: 7.15%, product B: 10.42%), and transportation (jeans laundry round trip), which averaged 1.16% for both products.

The impacts on PE related to cotton production and processing accounted for an average of 28.95% of the overall impacts for both companies. During this phase, the fertilizers potassium sulfate (K₂O), nitrogen (N), and phosphate (P₂O₅) were predominant, collectively contributing an average of 12.5% in this impact category. The application of fertilizers, pesticides, and agrochemicals has been identified as a significant factor contributing to eutrophication levels associated with cotton fiber production (Baydar et al., 2015; Bevilacqua et al., 2014; Bongiovanni & Tuninetti, 2018).

Weaving contributes an average of 11.6% to the PE's environmental burdens, mainly due to wood-fired heat generation. Clothing Manufacturing accounted for 27.7% of Company A's PE and 14.01% of Company B's PE, with energy consumption and transportation as the primary contributors. Low-voltage energy consumption in clothing manufacturing was 20.11% for product A and 9.49% for product B. Transportation of inputs and distribution accounted for 7.56% of impacts for company A and 4.5% for company B.

TA produced 2.01E-02 kg SO₂ eq for Company A's jeans and 2.93E-02 kg SO₂ eq for Company B's jeans. For product A, the most significant impact was from sewing, which contributed 38.98%, followed by cotton cultivation and

processing at 27.28%, jeans processing at 20.13%, and weaving at 13.55%. In the case of product B, jeans processing had the largest contribution at 40.49%, followed by cotton cultivation at 28.97%, sewing at 20.57%, and weaving at 9.90%.

The use of electricity and transportation input resulted in the highest values in the sewing phase for TA, corresponding to 27.06% and 11.14% of product A and 13.27% and 6.49% of product B, respectively. Conversely, the use of fertilizers (K_2O , N, P_2O_5) and pesticides (mancozeb, glyphosate) significantly impacted cotton cultivation on TA, collectively contributing an average of 16.9% for both companies. Energy consumption was notable in jeans processing, with TA contributions of 10.43% for product A and 15.79% for product B, attributed to Brazilian medium voltage electricity. For product B, tap water production contributed 19.82% at TA. Weaving showed significant heat production data, averaging 8.65% for both companies. For product A, the sewing phase contributed 40.58% to the POF indicator. In this phase, POF was influenced by transportation at 22.49% and energy consumption at 18.01%. Product B had 14.92% of its impact from transportation and 9.53% from energy consumption. The jeans processing phase was the most significant for POF, at 38.78%. This phase included impacts from tap water (21.87%), energy (11.66%), and transportation (3.52%). Weaving affected the category by 29.51% and 23.26% for the products of companies A and B, respectively, with a more significant impact from heat generation (product A: 27.09%; product B: 21.36%). In the Global Warming Potential category, the findings indicate that cotton production, jeans processing, and sewing contributed the most to CO_2 emissions in the manufacturing of jeans from companies A and B. CO_2 emissions were observed in processes involving energy generation and use (fossil and thermal). The contributions from cotton production and its processing are 1.27 kg CO_2 eq (22.42%) for product A and 1.98 kg CO_2 eq (23.81%) for product B. The impacts in cotton production and processing were

affected by the application of fertilizers (N, K₂O, P₂O₅) and pesticides (glyphosate, mancozeb).

Jeans processing also stood out in the GWP category, contributing 1.74 kg CO₂ eq (30.53%) and 4.14 kg CO₂ eq (49.72%) for products A and B, respectively. This was mainly due to energy production in tap water consumption (product A: 0.39 kg CO₂ eq, 6.85%; product B: 1.57 kg CO₂ eq, 18.81%) and energy consumption (product A: 0.62 kg CO₂ eq, 10.87%; product B: 1.37 kg CO₂ eq, 16.45%). These results reflect the national scenario, where the textile sector was the country's largest consumer of electricity, representing 64% of total energy consumption in 2016 (Empresa de Pesquisa Energética, 2017). Company A's jeans production emitted 2.35 kg CO₂ eq (41.25%), while Company B's emitted 1.82 kg CO₂ eq (21.92%) in the GWP category. Energy use contributed significantly (Product A: 1.53 kg CO₂ eq, 26.78%; Product B: 1.09 kg CO₂ eq, 13.13%), along with transportation of inputs (Product A: 0.754 kg CO₂ eq, 13.25%; Product B: 0.642 kg CO₂ eq, 7.71%).

3.3 Uncertainty analysis

The uncertainty assessment was conducted to ensure the robustness of the findings, allowing for the estimation of data variability and the reliability of conclusions. Table 2 presents the results of this analysis for each impact category considered in this study.

Table 2 - Uncertainty analysis results

Impact Category	Unity	Mean	Standard deviation	Mean	Standard deviation
		Company A	Company A	Company B	Company B
Water Scarcity	m ³	29.803	9.436E-04	1.062E2	1.044E-03
Eutrophication Potential	kg PO ₄ ⁻³ eq	9.914E-03	4.661E-05	1.5E-02	4.987E-05
Terrestrial Acidification	kg SO ₂ eq	2.00E-02	3.852E-05	2.9E-02	3.944E-05
Photochemical Oxidation Formation	kg NMVOC eq	1.70E-02	1.240E-05	2.3E-02	1.361E-05
Global Warming Potential	kg CO ₂ eq	5.697	3.258E-03	8.329	3.467E-03

Source: Authors.

According to the results, product B presents significantly higher means in all impact categories used in the study. The low standard deviations indicate high precision and reliability in data measurements. Using data within Brazilian context enhances representativeness in LCA studies. However, there is a need to build inventory databases with national data in the textile and clothing manufacture sector, as frequently noted by LCA researchers and practitioners (Becker Junior et al., 2017; De Brito & Da Silva, 2023; Silva et al., 2017). This necessity arises because generic data used in this study for upstream processes offer greater variation in the results, increasing uncertainties, despite its global averages ja (Azari Jafari et al., 2023)

4 DISCUSSION

The impact categories' results align with previous studies on the textile and clothing sector in Brazil. The variation in water scarcity between the two companies' jeans is due to differences in their processing methods. Product B requires more water as it undergoes additional treatments, including bleaching and rinsing, and is heavier than Product A. These treatments involve bleaching during the washing stage, followed by subsequent rinsing stages.

Processes requiring extensive washing significantly impact water footprint values (Chico et al., 2013). Wet processing often increases water use, ranging from 50 to 400 L/kg depending on fiber type and processing properties (Chico et al., 2013; Cinperi et al., 2019; Hussain & Wahab, 2018). Although water consumption varied significantly between the two companies, the percentages remained relatively close.

Although studies suggest that cotton fiber production requires high water consumption (J. Qian et al., 2020; W. Qian et al., 2021), the current study offers a different perspective within the Brazilian context. It finds that environmental performance is notably affected by the cultivation location (Pfister et al., 2009; Sandin et al., 2013). In areas with low rainfall, producers

frequently use irrigation technologies, which result in higher water usage and significant effects on the water scarcity footprint (Luo et al., 2022).

Sandin et al. (2013) highlight that the geographic location of supply chain operations in cotton fiber production is pivotal for evaluating water consumption impacts. Cotton farming in the Midwest region of Brazil, which largely employs non-irrigated systems, leads to a lower average water consumption compared to other regions in the country. Furthermore, the favorable climatic conditions in this area contribute to relatively low water usage (Chapagain et al., 2006).

Conventional cotton farming in Brazil leads to water, soil, and raw material contamination due to the use of pesticides and fuel. These practices also emit pollutants (F. Chen et al., 2021; Witkoski & Morgenstern, 2021). Although less than 1% of cotton production involves irrigation (Pfister et al., 2009), Brazil ranks as the fourth largest contributor to global water scarcity due to the textile sector's undimensioned water use (Peters et al., 2021).

The Brazilian Cerrado is recognized as a region well-suited for cotton cultivation due to its favorable topography, high-quality soil physical properties, and humid tropical climate. Nevertheless, the chemical quality of the soil is considered deficient, necessitating the application of soil amendments (Associação Mato-Grossense dos Produtores de Algodão, 2014; Carvalho, 2007). As a result, the use of these chemicals can impact soil and water quality, leading to environmental issues such as eutrophication and acidification, as observed in LCA study.

The use of agricultural inputs in cotton cultivation in Brazil remains a notable factor due to the quantities involved. This aspect needs to be addressed with more rigor. Carvalho and Ferreira (2006) note that cotton cultivation in the Brazilian Cerrado often involves the application of significant amounts of fertilizers to boost productivity. This practice can lead to the release of nutrients into the soil, which can also happen during the liming process to correct soil acidity (Pádua et al., 2008).

The application of fertilizers (K_2O , N, P_2O_5) and pesticides (mancozeb, glyphosate) played a critical role in influencing the impacts of cotton cultivation on TA and PE. Cotton cultivation requires soil renewal, which involves using fertilizers to provide necessary nutrients for proper plant growth (Carvalho, 2007). Thus, the LCA results align with the context of this type of cultivation in Brazil.

Company B's environmental impact was 52% higher than Company A's due to the greater use of chemicals in bleaching, neutralizing, and whitening jeans. This washing technique caused the difference. Textile industry effluents also increase eutrophication levels, explaining this result.

Agricultural inputs also influence greenhouse gas emission levels, contributing to GWP. Despite this result, in the Relatório Anual do Programa Brasileiro GHG Protocol (Fundação Getúlio Vargas, 2023), Scope 1 CO_2 emissions from agricultural activities and land-use change represent less than 1% of the national emissions. The production phases of jeans that required higher energy consumption, such as processing, weaving, and sewing, exhibited notable levels of CO_2 and POF emissions. Chen et al. (2023) examined the phases contributing most to the carbon footprint, based on LCA studies of cotton textile products. They identified weaving and sewing as having the greatest impact, while the raw material extraction stage for cotton showed a higher potential for carbon storage.

Thermal energy in processing stages uses natural gas, firewood, and oil, which emit greenhouse gases through machinery like boilers, thermal fluid heaters, and air compressors. These are major contributors to climate change (S. Chen et al., 2023).

In the Brazilian textile industry, the energy matrix is primarily composed of electricity, with natural gas and firewood being secondary sources. The adoption of natural gas, which is more readily available in urban centers, has supplanted other fuels, thereby reducing environmental pollution associated with combustion (Brazil, 2017). Brazil has potential for climate

change mitigation through the increased use of non-combustible renewable energy sources, such as wind and solar (Portugal-Pereira et al., 2018).

Another noteworthy result of the LCA study is the increased use of transportation, primarily road transport, which is prevalent in Brazil. This contributes to CO₂ emissions and raises the POF indicator. Regarding transportation, this outcome is consistent with national statistics, indicating that road transport accounts for 20.9% of the sector's CO₂ emissions, as reported by the (Confederação Nacional do Transporte (CNT), 2024).

Efforts should focus on establishing more sustainable distribution channels, particularly through fluvial and maritime transportation, leveraging the country's abundant water resources. The concentration of cotton production in the Center-West region of Brazil, especially in the Cerrado, benefits and encourages the formation of spinning and weaving companies in nearby regions, such as the South and Southeast (Mendes Júnior, 2021). This favors a greater concentration of companies, becoming a reference in the supply of raw materials for the textile sector, especially fabrics and yarns. The current infrastructure of the country's textile production chain influences the dynamics of clothing production in more distant regions, generating the intense use of road transport for the acquisition of raw materials from consolidated industrial hubs.

The existing infrastructure of the country's textile production chain affects clothing production in remote regions, leading to the extensive use of road transport to obtain raw materials from consolidated hubs. This can harm the Northeast, known for high clothing productivity, by increasing transportation and logistics costs due to company concentration in other areas. Additionally, this infrastructure affects the promotion of regional autonomy, which could help reduce environmental impacts and improve the efficiency of the production chain. A sensitivity analysis was conducted to observe changes in environmental impacts from redefining the textile supply chain, as detailed in the next section.

4.1 Sensitivity analysis

A sensitivity analysis was conducted, considering an alternative scenario (scenario 2) compared to the previously presented modeling (scenario 1). In this scenario, raw materials are sourced from companies located in Teresina, and a jeans processing laundry is established in the same production hub as the sewing factories.

Transportation was significant in four of the five impact categories analyzed by the LCIA. This study's findings on GWP align with national statistics, showing road transport accounts for 20.9% of CO₂ emissions in the sector, according to the National Transport Confederation (CNT, 2024).

In scenario 2, the jeans' round trip for processing in the laundry within the production hub was estimated. A distance of 4 km was established as a reasonable perimeter for this situation. Additionally, all raw materials for sewing jeans were sourced from suppliers located in the closest urban center, Teresina, which is 84 km away from the sewing factories. The results, compared with scenario 1, are presented in Table 3.

Table 3 - Results of sensitivity analysis and comparison between scenarios

Category	Unity	Scenario 1		Scenario 2		Reduction Potential (%)	
		Product A	Product B	Product A	Product B	Product A	Product B
Water Scarcity	m ³	29,80	106,15	29,72	106,08	- 0,27	- 0,07
Eutrophication Potential	kg PO ₄ ⁻³ eq	9,90E-03	1,51E-02	9,13E-03	1,43E-02	- 7.78	- 5.30
Terrestrial Acidification	kg SO ₂ eq	2.01E-02	2.93E-02	1,76E-02	2,70E-02	- 12.44	- 7.85
Photochemical Oxidation Formation	kg NMVOC eq	1.71E-02	2.31E-02	1.31E-02	1.94E-02	- 23.39	- 16.02
Global Warming Potential	kg CO ₂ eq	5.69	8.32	4,88	7,57	- 14.24	- 9.01

Source: Authors.

These results indicate a significant reduction in environmental impacts for the new scenario, with POF showing the highest percentage of reduction. Primary pollutants from motor vehicles are a main source of POF. Sourcing raw materials from nearby suppliers and installing laundry facilities in the production hub reduces transportation use, enhance energy efficiency, and improve resource utilization in the region.

The results indicate that modifications in the supply chain and incentives in local infrastructure can lower overall environmental impacts. For the supply chain, it is important to consider that selecting closer suppliers requires further analysis to assess the economic impact on purchasing inputs in urban centers near the sewing factories. Furthermore, each factory must include in its analysis various factors such as cost-benefit ratio, input quality, and other management considerations. Redirecting to local supply enhances the utilization of local labor, products, and services, thereby valuing regional resources and fostering local economic development.

Road freight transport represents 64.85% of the total transported freight in Brazil, while rail transport accounts for 14.95% (CNT, 2024). Larranaga et al. (2017) suggest that this disparity between transport methods highlights the necessity for alternatives to enhance competitiveness and facilitate the economic and sustainable development of the country. In this regard, rail and waterway transport are proposed as options to provide an intermodal alternative.

Brazil has 41,795 km of navigable waterways, though only 5.25% is utilized (CNT, 2024). Maintaining current sewing factory suppliers in the South and Southeast may work if alternative transport modes are used. Furthermore, less energy-intensive transport could cut costs, accidents, congestion, and pollution, but infrastructure limits hinder this shift in the short term (Machado Filho, 2009).

In this study, the materials used in accessories such as buttons and zippers, classified as non-ferrous metals, were included in the Life Cycle

Assessment (LCA). However, it was determined that these materials do not have significant environmental impacts. Therefore, it can be concluded that the exclusion of these accessories from LCA studies did not affect the overall impact results.

5 CONCLUSION

This study aimed to understand and analyze the operations and challenges in the manufacturing of jeans in a production hub in the Northeast of Brazil. The clothing industries in this region have great socioeconomic potential in the apparel sector but depend on raw materials supplied by hubs concentrated in the South and Southeast of the country. To promote more sustainable and effective development in the textile and clothing chain in the Northeast, it is essential to consider incentives for regional autonomy. This can contribute to reducing environmental impacts throughout the production hub. Therefore, opting for regional and local suppliers can be a viable alternative for companies in the Piauí hub.

DECLARATIONS

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